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Recreational value of El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park

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Abstract

In this paper, an estimate of recreational value of El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park is obtained by applying individual travel cost method. A consumer surplus or benefit of one visit (of one person) to this natural park has been estimated in 5.09 euros. This figure can provide information to stakeholders in order to determine recreational investments and to get a proper environment management and sustainable use of this place. As the model shows, people react to travel cost, and so, an entrance fee would reduce the number of visits in case of overcrowding. Nonetheless, given the profile of visitor, signalling and information about a proper use from an environmental point of view would be a socially preferable policy.

Key words: sustainable tourism; travel cost method; Natural Parks; recreational management

Introduction

Tourism has become an important economic sector but has also caused several unwanted economic, environmental and sociocultural impacts (Briassoulis, 2003). Problems as seasonality (Butler, 1994), overcrowding (Brouwer, Turner & Voisey, 2001), water scarcity for local people (Cole 2014) or local community annoyances (Lai & Hitchcock, 2017), between many others, have been recovered in the literature.

Environmental impacts of tourism are especially important since natural resources are limited and environment is also an important tourist attractiveness. There are many articles that study environmental problems related to tourism and some examples are going to be mentioned below. Araña & León (2016) used a field experiment to test the effectiveness of both non-market and market based sustainability policies in reducing overall CO₂ emission levels by affecting destination choice. Kuvan (2010) emphasises that monitoring and eliminating the negative environmental impacts of tourism is crucial for the protection and continuity of forest resources. Mejía & Brand (2007) say that the increase in demand for nature-based tourism brings economic and educational benefits but risks the introduction of invasive species. Moorhouse, D'Cruze & Macdonald (2017) point out unethical use of wildlife.

Ecotourism, nature-based and rural tourism are products that have grown steadily during last years. All of them have the nature, and especially natural parks, as core resources. Natural areas can feel the impact of human activity when tourism develops and problems of sustainability can emerge in these areas (Fleming & Manning, 2015). At the same time, nature based tourism can be one mean to help to achieve sustainability in the reserve areas (Salam, Lindsay & Beveridge, 2000). So, investment on environmental quality can be necessary for a good management of environment and tourism.

El Valle and Carrascoy is a natural park located in the southeast of Spain, with an increasing number of visitors given that it is closely located to important population centres. It is a recreational area with an important environmental value. In this natural park, as in many others all around the world, it is necessary that managers and institutions got to make the recreational use of these reserve areas compatible with their environmental conservation. One issue that can help in the achievement of environmental preservation is knowing the richness and value of natural parks. This paper estimates the recreational value of El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park, what can help to its tourist management and also to increase consciousness of surrounding population and institutions on the its environmental value. Individual travel cost methodology has been applied using data from questionnaires put in 2016 to a sample of 215 visitors. As a result, careful information is provided to authorities that manage this natural resource, what can help them to rely on cost-benefit analysis when designing policies regarding such a natural place.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Firstly, a literature review is presented. Secondly, El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park is introduced. Thirdly, methodology used is exposed that is applied in the following section in which major results are also shown. Finally, principal conclusions are exposed.

Literature review

Natural parks are used by visitors that frequently cause a negative impact. The value of these places and the possible damage caused by tourism is an important issue to be taken into account in tourism management (Palmer & Riera, 2003). Recent tourism studies have incorporated economic methods in order to attain valuation of environmental goods and damages, that do not have structured markets from which a market price, and hence, a reference market value could be obtained (Tisdell 2004).

Economic analysis approaches these issues by relying on a number of valuation methods (Folmer & Ierland, 1989). They can be divided into two big groups: direct or stated preferences methods (as contingent valuation or choice experiments) and indirect or revealed preferences methods (as travel cost or hedonic prices).

Directs methods obtain the value of an environmental good or a change in its supply through a direct statement of people. In them, a market is simulated. For example, in the contingent valuation method that uses a dichotomous answer in the valuation question, interviewed people are asked if they would pay a determined price for a good or an environmental improvement. Interviewee would say “yes” if the value of this improvement for him/her was greater than the cost (or price) suggested and would say “no” in the opposite case. It is as a hypothetical or simulated market. From these responses a valuation can be obtained through statistical technics (Hanemann, 1984).

Indirect methods obtain information from markets of goods that are related to the good whose value is trying to be determined. For example, travel cost method gets a valuation of a good from information about the cost of travel necessary to enjoy it.

These environmental economic methods have been incorporated in tourism studies, especially direct methods that have been used at least by Casey, Brown & Schuhmann (2010), C.K. Lee, Lee & Mjelde (2010), Hergesell & Dickinger (2013), M. Saayman & Saayman (2013), Choi & Ritchie (2014), Báez-Montenedro, Bedate-Centeno, Sanz-Lara & Herrero-Prieto (2015), Chiou, J.C. Lin, Liu & Lin (2016), Wuepper (2016) or Baral, Kaul, Heinen & Ale (2017). Indirect method seems to be less used and only Riera (2000), Mangan, Brouwer, Lohano & Nangraj (2013) and Wallentin (2016) are cited in this paper.

Casey et al. (2010) use a discrete choice contingent valuation experiment with almost 400 visitors to determine a measure of compensating variation for contributing to a public trust to protect corals. They estimate a mean willingness to pay (WTP) of over \$55.00. These results suggest that there are significant possibilities for implementing a “coral fund” to raise revenues for coral protection programs in the Riviera Maya region of Mexico’s Yucatan Peninsula. Lee et al. (2010) identify the activity and experience preferences of bird-watchers; they use choice experiment methods to estimate their willingness to pay for bird-watching-related ecotourism tour and interpretive services. Hergesell & Dickinger (2013) investigate the role of price, time and convenience regarding transport mode choice using a stated choice experiment. They used data from 372 European students resulting in 5952 choice situations and concluded that cost is the most important product attribute followed by time, with convenience playing a secondary role for student travellers. Mangan et al. (2013) estimated recreational value of Keenjhar lake in Pakistan using a travel cost model. M. Saayman & Saayman (2013) used

contingent valuation method to obtain the non-consumptive value or the appreciative value of the rhino, based on three surveys conducted in South Africa's Kruger National Park (KNP) from 2011 to 2013. They affirm that the non-consumptive value is greater than the consumptive value of rhino that is driven by the hunting price. Choi and Ritchie (2014) developed and applied a choice modelling study to measure the economic values of aviation carbon mitigation and to identify major factors influencing air travellers' voluntary climate action.

Results show that respondents have a mean willingness to pay (WTP) of AU\$21.38 per tonne of CO₂ reduced in the form of voluntary carbon offsets per person. Báez-Montenedro et al. (2015) determine the economic value assigned to the historical heritage of Valdivia (Chile) by tourists visiting the city using contingent valuation method. Chiou et al. (2016) applied contingent valuation method to evaluate the benefits of protective forests. For it, they used the willingness to pay for entrance to the Taitung Forest Park, that was estimated in NT\$21.7 for each person. Wallentin (2016) proposes a novel aggregated zonal travel cost model for estimating demand for a single recreation site when data are limited. Wuepper (2016) uses a choice experiment to value the World Heritage status for a German natural park. They find a per-person increase in willingness to pay of €4.70 which translates into an overall value increase of €3.8 million annually. Baral et al. (2017) estimate the economic value of World Heritage Site (WHS) designation for the Sagarmatha (Mount Everest) National Park, in Nepal, using the contingent valuation method. They obtained that median WTP amount was US\$90.93 per trip and 63.8% of visitors were willing to pay more than the existing entry.

El Valle and Carrascoy: A Natural Park in the Southeast of Spain

El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park is located in the southeast of Spain with an area of 17410 hectares that are spread about the municipalities of Murcia, Fuente Álamo and Alhama in the Region of Murcia, Spain. It's a natural park closely linked to local population, given its proximity to the city of Murcia and other villages and constitutes the major green lung in this area. Historical heritage resources starting from the Bronze Age, and passing through Iberian, Roman, Arab and Visigoth eras confers this area a huge historic, cultural and religious importance. It is part of Natura 2000 as a Site of Community Importance and Special Protection Area for birds sightseeing due to the presence of eagle owl among others species (Madrigal, 2015).

Land use corresponds to pasture (54%), forest (33%), fruit trees (6%) and other uses (7%). Agricultural use is decreasing; dry farming is located in flanks of hills and small basins between mountains and there are also some small areas of irrigated land in the west part. Goat and sheep farms are token although there is a potential for small game hunting. Mines exploitation (iron, copper and plaster) stopped in 1993 except small limestone production for construction and ornamentation. Nowadays, recreational use predominates in this site, especially in El Valle and Majal Blanco areas. There are historic remains as Iberian Sanctuary of the Light or the Arab Castle of La Asomada. The catholic Sanctuary of La Fuensanta is also a religious reference here; it was begun to be built in 1694 in baroque style and inside there are interesting pictures and reliefs. It is catalogued as a national monument. There exist five geologic interest places and some facilities for recreational use as an environmental education centre, parking, flora and fauna observatory, visitor centre, a youth hostel, a tree nursery, a botanic garden and recreational area. Guided visits are also organised. There is a wide net of signalled paths

all through this natural area, with a total signalled length of 60 km that includes a long route path (GR250 Cartagena-Caravaca de la Cruz) that travel around the park 11 km.

There are 18 different kinds of habitats of interest according to the European Union catalogue. Five of them, that occupy two thirds of the whole park, are included in Annex 1 of EU Habitat Directive since they are considered priority. There exists 55 species of catalogued plants, 48 of them included in the Regional Catalogue of Protected Wild Flora of the Region of Murcia; 33 are considered as species of special interest, 11 are considered as vulnerable and 4 in danger of extinction in the Region of Murcia. This park also has great fauna diversity due to the different vegetation structures arising. Birds constitute the most important group and some species are included in Annex 1 of Directive 79/409/CEE as golden eagle, real owl, peregrine falcon, short-toed eagle, wheatear or Bonelli's eagle (Alcón-Provencio, Martínez-Paz, Contreras-López & Navarro-Pay, 2015).

This natural area represents the regional environmental richness and provides cultural, recreational and environmental services that are very valued by local society. As a public good, despite of its owner of property, is a patrimony of all the citizens. So, it is important to know and quantify its social value and particularly its recreational value. In the next section the methodology used to attain this target is exposed.

Methodology

The travel cost method is going to be used in this article to estimate the recreational value of El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park. This method was firstly proposed by the prize novel Harold Hotelling, based on the surveys of Dupuit, giving rise to zonal travel cost method with equidistance. Different variants of the method has been used in environmental economics for over forty years.

The travel cost method allows estimation of the monetary value of non-marketed goods and services based on revealed preferences and is generally considered the most appropriate method to value recreational experiences (Haab & McConnell, 2002). It is based on the hypothesis that the expenditures made by the visitor to a recreational site, such as travel costs and entrance fees, can be used as surrogate prices to estimate the nonexistent prices for their recreational experience (Perman, Ma, McGilvary & Common, 2003).

Different concepts can be included in the cost of the travel. Between them the fuel expense or transport tickets, travel time, meal, overnight stay or the time of the visit. There is no unanimity between the authors about what of the mentioned concepts should be included in the travel cost except fuel or transport expense.

Travel cost method has several variants, zonal with equidistance, zonal without equidistance and individual (Riera, García, Kriström & Brännlund, 2005). The individual travel cost model has a number of advantages compared with the zonal travel cost model, including theoretical consistency in modelling individual behaviour and preference heterogeneity, avoidance of arbitrary zone definitions and statistical efficiency in estimating the choice model (Parsons, 2003). Individual method considers individual data

of visitors and the variable number of travel made in a determined period is a key variable. A function in which the number of travels in a period of time is explained by travel costs and other explicative variables is specified. A lineal function in which travel cost is the only explicative variable besides the constant is the easiest. Nonetheless, a Poisson or Negative Binomial model is normally used since they can reflect that number of travels/visits variable is not a continuous variable but a discrete one.

In statistical terms, Poisson model supposes a distribution of the kind

$$f(Travels) = \frac{e^{-(\lambda)} \lambda^{Travels}}{Travels!} \quad [1]$$

Where Travels! is factorial of the number of travels or visits made by a visitor during last year and λ is a value such that $\ln \lambda = a + b \text{cost}$, being λ the average of the number of visits, cost, the cost of the travel and \ln , natural logarithm function. Once “a” and “b” parameters are estimated, consumer surplus associated to one visit can be obtained as $1/b$.

In our survey, nonvisitors are not included in the sample, and therefore, the sample is truncated at zero. Taking into account that this fact can lead to biased and inconsistent estimates due to misspecification of the conditional mean, a zero-truncated Poisson model is going to be used to tackle this issue.

In this survey, the following truncated Poisson model is estimated

$$Pr(Travels_i = n \mid Cost_i, X_i) = \frac{e^{(-\lambda_i)} \lambda_i^n}{n!(1 - e^{-\lambda_i})}, n = 1, 2 \quad [2]$$

Where travel is the number of visits to the park made by the interviewed person during the last year, n is the number of observed visits for individual “i”, $cost_i$ is the travel cost for individual i , X_i is a vector of characteristics of individual i , and

$$\lambda_i \equiv E(Travels_i \mid n \mid Cost_i, X_i) = \exp(\beta Cost_i + \gamma X_i), \quad [3]$$

where β y γ are parameters to estimate. Hellerstein & Mendelson (1993) showed that consumer surplus can be obtained from the estimate of the average of the number of travels λ and β parameter, as λ/β .

Data are obtained from a sample of 215 visitors chosen randomly in different parts of El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park during the months of June and July of 2016. A structured questionnaire was used consisting of questions as the number of visits made during last year, recreational activities developed in the park, travel mode and expenditure associated, level of satisfaction of the visit or socioeconomic characteristics of interviewed person. All the interviewed visitors affirmed to have travelled to engage in recreational activities and did not visit any other site. A large majority revealed to have visited the park before. The visit used to last one morning or one afternoon.

Results

An estimate of recreational value of El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park is obtained by applying individual travel cost method. The sample characteristics will be commented before explaining the econometric results.

The typical visitor has previously enjoyed the area since 97% of the interviewed people stated having been previously and only 3% were visiting it for the first time. A high repetition rate exists since 60% of the sample stated to have visited the park more than 14 times during last year. This means that this park is very frequented by people living in the surrounding areas that use it as a recreational place. People access to the park mainly by car but also on foot and by bicycle. Principal activities during the visit are hill walking (87%), sightseeing (47%), having a picnic (40%) and flora and fauna observation (36%).

The level of satisfaction related to access, signposting, cleanness, flora and fauna, and general satisfaction was asked. Visitors are generally satisfied but cleanness and signposting received worse valuation than the others items. There was an open question about improvements in the park and a high percentage of visitors pointed two issues: signage on the trails and use indications that promoted users respect and conservation.

The socioeconomic profile of a typical visitor could be deduced from the following figures: 62% of interviewed visitors were male; 56% had university studies, 30% had secondary studies and 8% compulsory schooling; 46% are between 31 and 49 years old, 27% between 18 and 30 and 27% are older than 49 years old; 30% stated to have a level of income between 1000 and 1500 euros per month, 19% between 1000 and 1500 euros per month, 16% stated to have no income; 13% revealed to have a level of income greater than 2000 euros per month and 5% rejected to answer this question. Most of interviewed visitors stated to have an employment and 13% said to be unemployed.

Once sample characteristics have been commented, the econometric results are presented below.

The Poisson model estimated in this paper has the following form:

$$\ln(\lambda_i) = \gamma_0 + \beta \text{Cost}_i + \gamma_1 \text{Income}_i + \gamma_2 \text{Age}_i + \gamma_3 \text{Sex}_i \quad [4]$$

where Cost_i is the travel cost¹. A reference cost of 0.19 euros per kilometre has been used to translate to euros the distance covered. When an interviewed person travelled in group in the same private vehicle, the cost of the travel assigned was total expense of

¹ There is no unanimity about the concepts to include in travel cost when applying the method. All the authors agree including oil expense and transport tickets. Nonetheless, there is no agreement about including other concepts as meal expenses or the time of the visit. In this survey, a reference cost of 0.19 euros per kilometre has been used to translate to euros the distance covered; this is the quantity paid by the Spanish Administration when a civil servant uses his own car in a work travel; this quantity is the compensation for fuel and wear resulting from usage of the car. The time of the travel was not included. Given the park proximity to several cities, many visitors go on foot. This implies a longer travel for people that go on foot. When valuing the time of the travel, a paradox could emerge since people around the park could have a travel cost greater than people coming from more remote areas that came by car. That is why people coming on foot or by bicycle have been excluded in the estimate. The final sample used was of 98 visitors that came to the park by car.

the travel divided by the people in the group; $Income_i$ is the income per month of the visitor. Interviewed person was asked to choose one of five income intervals and the average of the interval chosen was assigned. Age_i and Sex_i were the age and sex of the interviewee.

Regression results are shown in the following table:

Table 1. Estimate of model [4]

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob
C	2.716013	0.099666	27.25114	0.0000
COST	-0.196335	0.011729	-16.73926	0.0000
INCOME	-0.000253	3.31E-05	-7.645440	0.0000
AGE	0.030568	0.001814	16.84845	0.0000
SEX	0.159705	0.050040	3.191546	0.0014
R-squared	0.570803			
Adjusted R-squared	0.552142			

We observe cost variable has a negative sign; the greater the travel cost is, the lower the number of visits made. Income variable also shows a negative sign. So, the greater the income of the visitor is, the smaller the number of visits made. So, visits to the park would be an inferior good. So, it could be inferred that the greater the income of a visitor is the smaller is the number of visits to this place since another leisure places and options would be available. Age has a positive sign; so, older people tend to visit the park more frequently. Sex variable (taking into account the way in which it was codified as a dichotomous one) has a positive sign, indicating that men visit more this area than women.

Taking $-1/\beta$ as consumer surplus associated to one visit, we obtain a consumer surplus for a visit of 5.09 euros. This is the benefit of the use of the El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park as a recreational place for a visit of one person that uses to last one morning or one afternoon. It can be considered a conservative value since other concepts of cost, as time cost opportunity, have not been included, and this method is sensitive to costs used. It can be also considered a realistic figure since it is quite acceptable as the expected benefit that a person could obtain from a visit lasting some hours. Conceptually, in this case, the consumer surplus is the difference between the willingness to pay of one person for the visit and the cost incurred to make it. This result is comparable with Mangan et al. (2013) that estimated the recreational value of Pakistan's largest freshwater lake using individual travel cost method. They obtained a consumer surplus of US\$ 14 (11.2 euros) per person per visit. Differences in the lasting of the visit, the level of income of visitors (this lake is visited by persons with medium-high level of income) and characteristics of the environmental goods, make logical differences in consumer surpluses. The results of the other two papers cited in this survey that use travel cost methods, Wallentin (2016), are not comparable to ours since methodology and research objectives are different.

We should remind that this is not the total value of the park but the recreational one since other non-use values are not measured by this method.

Conclusion and implications

El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park is one of the most extensive protected natural areas in the Region of Murcia, Spain. Its proximity to the city of Murcia and other villages has turned this area into the most visited natural park by the inhabitants of the region and, potentially, this territory may suffer an important human impact. During last years, this natural park has acquired a recreational profile for the enjoyment of people together with a possible decline in its environmental quality and use. In this way, it has become necessary the implementation of protection policies that allowed a sustainable use of the park.

Nonetheless, in protected natural areas with high visitation, tourism and conservation can combine for a sustainable symbiotic relationship where tourism helped to maintain ecosystems since a part of visitors' expenditures can be destined to nature protection.

This paper has put the first stone in this way, as a mean of helping the stakeholders to improve the management and protection of such natural asset by proving a valuation of one visit and a clear visitor profile. This is a useful information for decision making and cost-benefit analysis.

The research has computed the recreational value of one visit of one person to the El Valle and Carrascoy Natural Park by relying on the individual travel cost method. Nonetheless, as this method allows us to value only recreational use, further work is needed to complete the picture of the environmental value of the park. Results obtained provide information on its recreational or tourist value to users and institutions in charge of its management. A consumer surplus or benefit of one visit (of one person) to this natural environment has been estimated in 5.09 euros. If total visitors figure was available, a total tourist valuation could be obtained, that had to be taken into account in the decision-making and policy design process that affected this area.

As people react to prices and the entrance to the park is free, we can deduce that an entrance fee would reduce the number of visitors and could be an instrument in case of overcrowding. Besides, in the case of public sector financial help scarcity, the revenue obtained in this way could support its sustainable management. Nonetheless, given that is a recreational and environmental good without closed substitutive places and that we could infer it is used by people with less leisure substitutive goods (we obtained a negative relation between level of income and number of visits) we could think an entrance fee was not socially advisable. It seems more acceptable to increment signalling and information about a proper use since these are also the major demands stated by visitors. Given data of total visitors and the value of a visit estimated in this paper, we could infer the level of public investment in recreational aspects of the park that is socially desirable.

The use of experiment choice could allow us to obtain other values of this area, as the environmental ones, and even valuations of different tourist activities. These would be possible future extensions of this research.

References

- Alcón-Provencio, F., Martínez-Paz, J.M., Contreras-López, S. & Navarro-Pay, N. (2015). *Caracterización y evaluación de preferencias de desarrollo de los principales espacios naturales del Grupo de Acción Local Campoder* [Characterization and Evaluation of Preferences of Development of major natural areas of Local Action Group Campoder]. Murcia: Ed. Campoder.
- Araña, J.E. & León, C.J. (2016) Are tourists animal spirits? Evidence from a field experiment exploring the use of non-market based interventions advocating sustainable tourism. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 24(3), 430-445, DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2015.1101128
- Báez-Montenedro, A., Bedate Centeno, A., Sanz Lara, J.A. & Herrero Prieto, L.C. (2015). Contingent valuation and motivation analysis of tourist routes. Application to the cultural heritage of Valdivia (Chile). *Tourism Economics*, 22(3), 558–571. DOI: /10.5367/te.2015.0459
- Baral, N., Kaul, S., Heinen, J.T. & Ale, S.B. (2017): Estimating the value of the World Heritage Site designation: a case study from Sagarmatha (Mount Everest) National Park, Nepal, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2017.1310866
- Briassoulis, H. (2003). Crete: Endowed by Nature, Privileged by Geography, Threatened by Tourism? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 11(2-3), 97-115, DOI: 10.1080/09669580308667198
- Brouwer, R., Turner, R.K. & Voisey, H. (2001) Public Perception of Overcrowding and Management Alternatives in a Multi-purpose Open Access Resource, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 9(6), 471-490, DOI: 10.1080/09669580108667415
- Butler, R. (1994). Seasonality in tourism: Issues and problems. In A. Seaton Ed. *Tourisms. The status of the art* (pp 332-339). Chichester: Wiley.
- Casey, J.F., Brown, C. & Schuhmann, P. (2010) Are tourists willing to pay additional fees to protect corals in Mexico? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 18(4), 557-573, DOI: 10.1080/09669580903513079
- Chiou, C.R., Lin, J.C., Liu, W.Y. & Lin, T.W. (2016). Assessing the recreational value of protective forests at Taitung Forest Park in Taiwan. *Tourism Economics*, 22(5), 1132–1140. DOI: 10.5367/te.2015.0468
- Choi, A.S. & Ritchie, B.W. (2014) Willingness to pay for flying carbon neutral in Australia: an exploratory study of offsetter profiles. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 22(8), 1236-1256, DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2014.894518.
- Cole, S. (2014). Tourism and water: from stakeholders to rights holders and what tourism businesses need to do. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 22, 1. DOI:10.1080/09669582.2013.776062
- Fleming, C.M., & Manning, M. (2015). Rationing access to Protected Natural Areas: An Australian Case Study. *Tourism Economics*, 21(5), 995-1014. DOI:10.5367/te.2014.0388
- Folmer, H. & Ierland, E.C. (1989). *Valuation methods and Policy Making in Environmental Economics*. H. Folmer E.C. van Ierland Editors.
- Haab, C.H. & McConnell, K. (2002). *Valuing environmental and natural resources: The econometrics of non-market valuation*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.

- Haneman, W.M. (1984). "Welfare Evaluations in Contingent valuation Experiment with Discrete Responses". *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 63(3), 332-341. DOI:ffzkv7.
- Hellerstein, N.D., & Mendelson, R. (1993). A theoretical foundation for Count Data Models. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 75(3), 604-611.
- Hergesell, A. & Dickinger, A. (2013). Environmentally friendly holiday transport mode choices among students: the role of price, time and convenience. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 21(4), 596-613, DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2013.785555
- Kuvan, Y. (2010). Mass Tourism Development and Deforestation in Turkey. *Anatolia*, 21(1), 155-168. DOI:10.1080/13032917.2010.9687096
- Lai, I.K.W., & Hitchcock, M. (2017) Local reactions to mass tourism and community tourism development in Macau. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 25(4), 451-470. DOI:10.1080/09669582.2016.1221413
- Lee C.K., Lee, J.H., Kim, T.K. & W. Mjelde, J.W. (2010). Preferences and willingness to pay for bird-watching tour and interpretive services using a choice experiment, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 18(5), 695-708, DOI: 10.1080/09669581003602333
- Madrigal de Torres, J. (2015). Oficina de Impulso Socioeconómico del Medio Ambiente (OISMA). *Memoria Anual de Gestión de 2015 Parque Regional El Valle y Carrascoy [2015 Annual Management Report of El Valle and Carrascoy Natutal Park]*. Murcia: Ed. CARM.
- Mangan, T., Brouwer, R., Lohano, H.D. & Nangraj, G.M. (2013) Estimating the recreational value of Pakistan's largest freshwater lake to support sustainable tourism management using a travel cost model. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 21(3), 473-486, DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2012.708040.
- Mejía, C.V. & Sylvia Brandt, S. (2017) Utilizing environmental information and pricing strategies to reduce externalities of tourism: the case of invasive species in the Galapagos. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 25(6), 763-778, DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2016.1247847
- Moorhouse, T., D'Cruze, N.C. & Macdonald, D.W. (2017). Unethical use of wildlife in tourism: what's the problem, who is responsible, and what can be done? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 25(4), 505-516. DOI:10.1080/09669582.2016.1223087
- Palmer, T. & Riera, A. (2003). Tourism and environmental taxes. With special reference to the "Balearic ecotax". *Tourism Management* 24, 665-674.
- Parsons, G.R. (2003). The travel cost model. In P.A. Champ, K.J. Boyle & T.C. Brown (Eds), *A primer on nonmarket valuation*. Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Perman, R., Ma, Y., McGilvary, J. & Common, M. (2003). *Natural resources and environmental economics*. Harlow: Pearson Education.
- Riera Font, A. (2000). Mass Tourism and the Demand for Protected Natural Areas: A Travel Cost Approach. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 39(1), 97-116.
- Riera, P., García, D., Kriström, B. & Brännlund, R. (2005). *Manual de Economía Ambiental y de los Recursos Naturales [Environmental and Natural Resource Economics Handbook]* Madrid: Ed. Thomson Paraninfo.

- Saayman, M. & Saayman, A. (2017) Is the rhino worth saving? A sustainable tourism perspective. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 25(2), 251-264, DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2016.1197229
- Salam, M.A., Lindsay, G.R. and Beveridge, M.C.M. (2000). Eco-tourism to Protect the Reserve Mangrove Forest the Sundarbans and its Flora and Fauna. *Anatolia*, 11(1), 56-66. DOI: 10.1080/13032917.2000.9686983
- Tisdell, C. (2004). *Nature-based Tourism and the Valuation of its Environmental Resources: Economic and other aspects*. Working paper 104, The University of Queensland, ISSN 1327-8231.
- Wallentin, E. (2016). Choice of the angler. Estimating single-site recreation demand using revealed preference data. *Tourism Economics*, 22(6), 1338–1351. DOI: 10.5367/te.2015.0486
- Wuepper, D. (2016) What is the value of world heritage status for a German national park? A choice experiment from Jasmund, 1 year after inscription. *Tourism Economics*, 23(5), 1114–1123. DOI:10.1177/1354816616655958

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